

THE LINGUISTICS ASPECTS OF THE SPEECH UNITS AND ITS NOMINATIVE FEATURES

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Abstract:

This article deals with linguistics aspects of the speech units and its nominative features. The initial form of the evolution of thinking is in a nonverbal state, its formation is connected with language. In this process, it invariably correlates with the language system. Since, whatever he speaker thinks, it is realized only through language. In other words, it is difficult to imagine thinking without language. Language not only gives verbal expression to thinking – it involves a certain force necessary for its development.

Key words: speech units, synergy, syntactic structure, language, speech, communicative function

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/3enn0d79>

In the 20th century in linguistics, it is necessary to differentiate between language and speech as a great positive event. This is important, even nowadays, some linguists consider language and speech as a common phenomenon. F. de Saussure was scientifically based on the "language and speech" dichotomy. However, the essence of this issue is justified. The proof of that is that today's speech linguistics has received a special scientific status. This, of course, is bound to the name of Saussure. When he read a lecture on general linguistics for students at the University of Geneva, he emphasized: "Yes, ladies and gentlemen, about the same linguistics, but I dare to say that the area of this linguistics is very extensive and it consists of two parts: one is closer to the language, a passive stock, the other is closer to the speech and is an active force ...".

In fact, the anthropocentric course in linguistics has come to our forefront in the 70's of the last centuries was. The proof of that is that a large part of the French language linguist Emil Benvenist's "General Linguistics" is called "Man and the Language" ("Человек и язык").: "It is in language and through language that a person is constituted as a subject, for only language lends reality, its reality, which is the property of being-the concept of Ego - "mine, I".

As noted above, the human factor in the development of language and its practical application has not been adequately addressed so far. However, this does not mean that the issue of human factor is neglected in linguistics. It is noteworthy that the well-known linguist Vonn Humboldt did not comment on the issue of human factor in studying the philosophical issues of the language. The issue of language and thinking is always in the spotlight of our linguists.

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The current issues of cognitive linguistics are being studied in the name of philosophy of the theory of knowledge. It is only a novelty that a linguist acquired his linguistic status today.

In this case, though we have to retreat, we have to pause briefly about the phrase and phrase. Both sentences and phrases are actively used in our language. But with the sentence; not common concepts. The concept of cumulus often includes all the syntactic structures used in our speech. The concept of speech calls for a grammatical category.

Emil Benvenist emphasizes that an individual act, which is an important tool in utilizing language, will first activate the speaker as a speech process. It emphasizes that the language will exist as a unique opportunity until the sentence is formulated and that the speech process will become an active tool that will enable the human to operate through sounds.

In our opinion, the pragmatic activity of the speaker begins and the gradual transformation of the linguistic units into the speech from each sentence begins. In other words, the inductive method of speaking in linguistic units is activated, and the result is the text. From a pragmatic perspective, the speaker's illogical plan will be fulfilled.

Of course, all of these events are related to the communicative process, because the speaker (human factor) is important. U.L. Chafe emphasizes that the psychological state of the speaker and the listener is also important. He believes that the semantic structures associated with the thought are transformed into phonological structures in the human brain, thereby creating an inextricable relationship with the linguistic thought process. It is difficult for any language phenomenon to be examined without human thinking, in other words, what is happening in his mind.

According to E.Paducheva, many words cannot mean independent meaning. The word that comes out of context is, in most cases, very meaningful and, when used in the sentence, implies a meaningful unity (nomadic unity). In addition, the word used in the sentence is indefinable, but the general meaning of the sentence may not necessarily be the same as the meaning of these words. This type of description of the problem indicates that each word (or a nomadic unit of the language) can only perform certain functions in a context, a syntactical chain of chains, and have a certain meaning [5, 12].

The language system can be divided into two ways:

1. Methodology as a logical principle.

2. The language of the immanent (non-external influences) character. Of course, these concepts are interdependent and require the existence of the other one. However, while studying the functional value of language units, the latter is of the utmost importance. The main reason for this is that the language system (in the case of an imminent characteristic system) has synergetic power. If you see that synergetic is self-governance, then the language system does not require explanation [4].

At the same time, we emphasize the notion of the language system. But we do not want to deny that speech is a complex system. Of course, the speech is also supported by this synergetic force. Human factor participation is inevitable. At the same time, however, the speech has only relevant aspects, and their functional activity relies on synergetic power.

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